

MACHINES AND ROBOTICS USED IN LIVESTOCK AND FOOD INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

Livestock and food industry can be profitable if it reduces labour cost. The application of machines and robotics have been successfully achieved in a wide range of manufactured industries dealing with well-defined processes and products. Robotics have certain limitations and challenges, but robots have potential to change our economy, health, living and the world we live in.

KEY WORDS: Machines, Robotics, Economy, Heath, Living

INTRODUCTION

Livestock and food industry are highly labor-intensive, consisting labor costs could be up to 50% of the product cost. Improving productivity and reducing labor costs will therefore have a significant impact on profitability. Much of the manual work in livestock and food industry requires rapid, repetitive, and monotonous movement and, consequently, low levels of motivation among workers. This leads to poor quality control and a high incidence of industrial accidents which can be reduced by the application of machines and robotics in these industries. Use of machines for various processing in livestock and food industry are considered as automated systems which are capable of performing their functions with greater accuracy and precision, and in less time, than humans. The application of machines (automation) and robotics have been successfully achieved in a wide range of manufactured industries dealing with well-defined processes and products.

Robotics is the branch of technology that deals with the design, construction, operation, and application of robots, as well as computer systems for their control, sensory feedback, and information processing. These technologies deal with automated machines that can take the place

of humans in dangerous environments or manufacturing processes, or resemble humans in appearance, behaviour, and/or cognition. Robot came from the Czechoslovakian word, "robota" meaning forced labor. The International Standards Organization (ISO) defines a robot as, "An automatically controlled, re-programmable, multi-purpose, manipulative machine with several degrees of freedom, which may be either fixed in place or mobile for use in industrial automation applications."

CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH THE USE OF ROBOTS IN THESE INDUSTRIES

- (1) The objects being handled are variable in size, shape, weight and position, so that some form of intelligent sensing is required.
- (2) The objects to be handled are often delicate and covered with either slippery or viscous substances, and so the end effect or must be carefully designed if it is to handle the objects at high speed with secure lifting and without bruising.
- (3) The concern for hygiene, quality and consumer safety. The hygiene issue is becoming increasingly important for human health.

But all the three challenges have been accepted by modern robots